

Ultraviolet Absorption of the Derivatives of α-Isonitrosocyanoacetic Acid

A. M. Talati and T. I. Patel

In continuation of our studies on the system¹ (A), a related system (B) has been investigated:

(where R=O or N). The results obtained (Table I) for the UV absorption spectra of the derivatives of α-isonitrosocyanoacetic acid (C-acid) in water and methanol have been discussed.

Chromophore.—The absorption band (A) at 228-34 mμ. observed in the case of C-acid derivatives in water and methanol, is attributed to the crossed conjugated system:

Since the absorption bands of diacetyl dioxime and αβ-bis-hydroxyiminobutyranilide in methanolic solutions are at 227 mμ and 236-38 mμ respectively, it is considered that π-electron system of C≡N group in C-anilide is partially localised on the group and hence the extension of the conjugation is weakened.

TABLE I

Compound.	In water.		In Methanol.	
	max.	<i>E</i> _m .	λ _{max} .	<i>E</i> _m .
C-anilide	231-32 mμ	11685	233-34 mμ	22970
	294-98	8500	298-99	4710
C-amide	228	7400	229-30	3560
	283-85	6850	284-86	5100
C-ethyl ester	232-34	3500	232-33	5080
	284-85	12150	288-90	10800

Besides, there is a second absorption band (B) at 283-99 mμ in the solutions under investigation and it is attributed to the existence of their ionic tautomers.

1. Talati *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 1592; this *Journal*, under publication.

Solution Effect.—No shift is observed when the absorption band (A) of C-amide is compared with that of diacetyl monoxime. Hence it may be considered that the conjugative effect of carbonyl group in diacetyl monoxime will be similar to that of nitrile and amide groups in C-amide. On the other hand, the band of C-ethyl ester or of C-anilide shows a red shift when compared with the band of C-amide or of diacetyl monoxime and is considered to indicate an increase in conjugation in these systems.

Solvent Effect.—When we compare the absorption bands of C-acid derivatives in methanol with those in water, we find that the band undergoes a slight blue shift as the polarity of the solvent is increased and this is attributed to the absence of solute-solvent interaction.

The B-band is less intense in methanolic solution than in aqueous solution. This might result from the decreased ionisation of the oxime group in alcoholic solution.

α -Isonitrosocyanacetanilide², α -isonitrosocyanacetamide³, and ethyl α -isonitrosocyanacetate³ were prepared by the known methods.

The UV absorption spectra of the solutions were investigated with a Beckman Model DU spectrophotometer, using 1 cm matched quartz cells.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
M. S. UNIVERSITY,
BARODA.

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2. Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1903, 41, 4076.

3. Conrad and Schutze, *Ber.*, 1900, 42, 735.